

Modeling Amide-I stretching in ChannelRhodopsin2

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Channel-Rhodopsin2 Function

Channel-Rhodopsin-2 (**ChR2**) is a light-gated cation-selective **ion channel**

Photo-isomerization of the retinal cofactor induces the channel opening

ChR2 is one of the most used **optogenetic tool** in neurosciences

Mutation influence on photo-cycle

Residue **mutations** which influence hydrogen bond network (HBN) have shown **strong effect on function and kinetic of the photo-cycle(PC)**.

Arginine 120 links retinal to the exit of the ion channel. R120H mutation provides an active photo-cycle, but no channel opening.

Mutation influence on photo-cycle

Differential and time-resolved IR spectroscopy has been used to track **conformational changes** along the photo-cycle

1580 and 1664 cm^{-1} : **Amide modes**
1655, 1638 cm^{-1} : retinal **C=N stretching**

IR spectra calculation via PMM

Amide1 mode as function of mutation

Exp amide-I

WT: 1664 cm^{-1}
R120H : 1657 cm^{-1}

Theo. amide-I

WT: 1650 cm^{-1}
R120HIE: 1650 cm^{-1}
R120HIP: 1650 cm^{-1}

Calculations shows similar behavior as the experiments, HIS120 mutation do not produce significant modification in the amide-I mode in the dark-state of ChR2.

